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Data Management Plan

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Editor(s):	Mir Ghoraishi (GIGASYS)
Author(s) and Contributor(s):	Mir Ghoraishi (GIGASYS) Jesús Gutiérrez (IHP) Simon Pryor (ACC)
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List of Acronyms

DMP	Data Management Plan
DoW	Description of Work
DPO	Data Protection Officer
EEA	European Economic Area
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
ePD	ePrivacy Directive
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
IT	Information Technology
WP	Work Package

Executive Summary

This document presents the data management guideline, according to the GDPR [1], for all activities related to BeGREEN project. As any other research and development project, BeGREEN produces data in different formats in the format of various types of documents and electronic files. Therefore, it is essential for the project and consortium to have clear guidelines on how to produce, handle, store, and share this data. To this end, the consortium has adhered to the H2020 ORDP (Open Research Data Pilot) [2] convention with the EC, which explicitly caters for the delivery of a DMP (Data Management Plan).

This document, BeGREEN D1.3, describes both the set of principles to guide the data collection and preservation and the ongoing and future activities handling with data, before and even after the project is completed.

Detailed information included in the DMP are data management lifecycle for all data sets that will be collected, processed, or generated by the consortium during the project related research and developments. The procedures on how research data will be handled during the project, and even after the project is completed are outlined. These guidelines describe what data will be collected, processed, or generated and following what methodology and standards, whether and how this data will be shared and/or made open, and how it will be curated and preserved.

Three main data scenarios are envisaged:

- Original data produced by the consortium and/or individual members of it (e.g., during the piloting activities, the case studies research and the dissemination activities);
- Existing data already in possession of the consortium and/or individual members of it prior to the project's initiation;
- Existing data sourced/procured by the consortium and/or individual members of it during the project's timeline.

Finally, it is reminded that the DMP presented in BeGREEN D1.2 is a living document and future releases, if needed, will be adapted to the needs and processes of the experiments and trials, taking in consideration the GDPR guidelines and the project evolution.

1 Introduction

The main goal of BeGREEN is to develop beyond-5G innovative technologies, targetting on design and implementation of innovative solutions to enhance energy efficiency radio access network, and to test and demonstrate these solutions. The project results will be validated using predefined KPIs, in both controlled set-ups and realistic scenarios. The project final proof-of-concept demonstrations will involve participants from the project partners. No participant from the general public is expected to take part in the demonstrations. Neither any of the proof-of-concept will use any personal data from public or partners employees. The users in the experimentations activities in work package 5 (WP5) ‘Solutions Implementation and Demonstrations’, are from partners employees. Nevertheless, this deliverable provides guidelines and considerations related to preservation of privacy, i.e., personal data, and to get the participants’ consent to use the data they provide, *if applicable*, for research purposes.

Key results and lessons learnt from the experimentation on the platforms will be for validating the performance of the implemented technologies in order to be ready for future use by broad the community, i.e., related industries, research and academic centres, startups and technologists. Although the involvement of human participants is not expected (will be very limited, if any), in BeGREEN demonstrations and the validation of the KPIs does not rely on processing any personal data, BeGREEN work plan includes the definition of specific schemes and measures in order to check the compliance of the activities with the respective legal framework and regulations as well as to minimize any potential data privacy leak or risk.

The purpose of this document is to describe the procedures to manage, store, share, and exchange data among BeGREEN consortium members and with the community. This includes the processes that partners will follow to comply with privacy, security and data protection according to the related legal and ethical guidelines.

1.1 Overview

The deliverable is organised in the following chapters:

- Chapter 1 describes the data management lifecycle and frames based on which the DMP needs to be detailed according to the EU commission guidelines and FAIR data handling principles,
- Section 2 is a brief review of the legal framework, including the EU regulation on GDPR (personal data protection) and the Horizon Europe provisions for open access to research data based on which the DMP is planned,
- Section 3 presents BeGREEN DMP, in which the data usage and scenarios are detailed and the key issues to be examined in relation to each scenario are discussed. These issues include decisions on data anonymisation, privacy, security and protection, licensing, and so on.
- Section 5 is the summary of the document.

2 Legal Framework

2.1 EU general data protection regulation (GDPR)

The GDPR Regulation (EU) 2016/679 [1] is a European Union law which entered into force in 2016 and, following a two-year transition period, became directly applicable law in all member states of the European Union on 25 May 2018, without requiring implementation by the EU member states through national law. It is notably concerning the processing of personal data belonging to EU citizens by individuals, companies, or public sector/non-government organisations, irrespective of their localization. It is therefore a primary matter of concern for the BeGREEN consortium. A 'Regulation' (unlike the Directive which it replaced) is directly applicable and has a consistent effect on all member states. However, there remain more than 50 areas covered by GDPR where member states are permitted to legislate differently in their own domestic data protection laws, and there continues to be room for different interpretation and enforcement practices among the member states. The GDPR text is available on the Eur-Lex website [1].

The GDPR provisions do not apply to the processing of personal data of deceased persons or of legal entities. They do not apply either to data processed by an individual for purely personal reasons or activities carried out at home, provided there is no connection to a professional or commercial activity. When an individual uses personal data outside the personal sphere, for socio-cultural or financial activities for example, the data protection law needs to be respected.

On the other hand, the legislative definition of personal data is quite broad, as it includes any information relating to an individual, whether it relates to his or her private, professional, or public life. It can be anything from a name, a home address, a photo, an email address, bank details, posts on social networking websites, medical information, or a computer's IP address.

The GDPR Regulation (EU) 2016/679 rules relate to the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and rules relating to the free movement of personal data, and applies to all matters concerning the protection of fundamental rights and freedoms vis-à-vis the processing of personal data which are not subject to specific obligations with the same objective set out in ePrivacy Directive 2002/58/EC [3].

The ePrivacy Directive (ePD) harmonises the provisions of the member states required to ensure an equivalent level of protection of fundamental rights and freedoms, and in particular the right to privacy, with respect to the processing of personal data in the electronic communication sector and to ensure the free movement of such data and of electronic communication equipment and services in the Community, particularise and complement GDPR.

Primarily, the application of the GDPR turns on whether an organization is established in the EU. An 'establishment' may take a wide variety of forms and is not necessarily a legal entity registered in an EU member state. However, the GDPR also has extra-territorial effects. An organization that it is not established within the EU will still be subject to the GDPR if it processes personal data of data subjects who are in the Union where the processing activities are related "to the offering of goods or services" (Article 3(2)(a)) (no payment is required) to such data subjects in the EU or "the monitoring of their behaviour" (Article 3(2)(b)) as far as their behaviour takes place within the EU.

According to article 89 of GDPR Regulation (EU) 2016/679, processing for scientific research purposes or statistical purposes shall be subject to appropriate safeguards in accordance with this Regulation for the rights and freedoms of the data subject. Those safeguards shall ensure that technical and organisational measures are in place in particular to ensure respect for the principle of data minimisation. Those measures may include pseudonymisation provided that those purposes can be fulfilled in that manner. Where those purposes can be fulfilled by further processing which does not permit or no longer permits the identification

of data subjects, those purposes shall be fulfilled in that manner.

According to article 95 GDPR shall not impose additional obligations on natural or legal persons in relation to processing in connection with the provision of publicly available electronic communications services in public communication networks in the Union in relation to matters for which they are subject to specific obligations with the same objective set out in Directive 2002/58/EC. This Regulation should apply to all matters concerning the protection of fundamental rights and freedoms vis-à-vis the processing of personal data which are not subject to specific obligations with the same objective set out in Directive 2002/58/EC, including the obligations on the controller and the rights of natural persons.

From the date GDPR came into force, Directive 2002/58/EC will be reviewed in particular to ensure consistency with GDPR and in order to clarify the relationship between this Regulation and Directive 2002/58/EC, that Directive should be amended accordingly.

Key definitions of the GDPR are:

- **Personal data:** Any information relating to an identified or identifiable natural person ('data subject')
- **Processing:** Any operation or set of operations which is performed on personal data or on sets of personal data, whether by automated means, such as collection, recording, organisation, structuring, storage, adaptation or alteration, retrieval, consultation, use, disclosure by transmission, dissemination or otherwise making available, alignment or combination, restriction, erasure or destruction

Key actors from the GDPR are:

- **Controller:** The natural or legal person, public authority, agency, or other body which, alone or jointly with others, determines the purposes and means of the processing of personal data
- **Processor:** A natural or legal person, public authority, agency, or other body which processes personal data on behalf of the controller

Each partner of BeGREEN consortium should determine its own role per case, but it is also expected to have the status of a controller and the data subject will refer to:

- External participants to the tests
- Employees of the BeGREEN beneficiaries
- Researchers of the BeGREEN beneficiaries

The data subjects will have the following rights:

- Right of access
- Right to rectification
- Right to erasure ('right to be forgotten')
- Right to restriction of processing

Each BeGREEN partner acting as a controller according to GDPR must comply with the following requirements:

- Shall take appropriate measures to provide any information relating to processing to the data subject
- Shall facilitate the exercise of data subject rights
- Shall provide information on action taken on a request to the data subject without undue delay and in any event within one month of receipt of the request
- Shall implement appropriate technical and organisational measures to ensure and to be able to demonstrate that processing is performed in accordance with this Regulation, both at the time of the determination of the means for processing and at the time of the processing itself, e.g. anonymization, pseudonymization.
- Shall implement appropriate technical and organisational measures for ensuring that, by default, only personal data which are necessary for each specific purpose of the processing are processed.

- If during the project, processing will take place under the authority of the controller or processor, the processor and any person acting under the authority of the controller or of the processor, who has access to personal data, shall not process those data except on instructions from the controller, unless required to do so by Union or member state laws which comply to GDPR.

For GDPR it is of utmost importance for the lawfulness of processing that:

- The data subject has given his/her written consent** to the processing of his or her personal data for one or more specific purpose;
- Processing is necessary for the performance of a contract** to which the data subject is party or in order to take steps at the request of the data subject prior to entering into a contract;
- Processing is necessary for compliance with a legal obligation to which the controller is subject;** For the ePrivacy Directive (ePD) the data subject to give his/her consent and clear and comprehensive information in accordance with Directive 95/46/EC (now GDPR), and that he/she is offered the right to refuse or the possibility to withdraw their consent for the processing (for traffic data) at any time.
- Every partner to act in a fair, lawful and transparent way.** For that to happen information notices such as informed consent forms need to be clearly written and presented. Ensure that data subjects have explained in their privacy policies and notices what they consider their legitimate interests to be and included in research activities.
- Data minimization:** researchers should try to minimise the amount of personal data held. De-identify or pseudonymise data by removing identifying details as early in the process as is feasible. If a data subject communicates, the partner will need to facilitate the minimization process by not further processing identification data. However, if the responses have already been incorporated and anonymised, then the data does not have to be deleted as it is not personal data.
- Storage limitation:** The process should be taken to minimise the level of personal data held for research purposes. It is only applicable to personal identifiable data and not to responses that cannot be linked. Retention periods must be established for personal data, and data subjects be informed of the period, or the criteria used in deciding how long the data will be kept for. Retention periods should only be for as long as the personal data is required.
- Accountability:** Records of decision made on legitimate interests, data protection impact assessments and the appointment or non-appointment of a Data Protection Officer are all important in demonstrating accountability. The IT systems need to be able to record and demonstrate consents and facilitate the exercise of all individual rights including rights to access data and withdraw from the research at any time.

In case there are participants in any of project's tests, including both employees and researchers, any processing of their data (if any) should take place only upon their written consent. Each partner, is committed to take into account and address the major risks in data protection and privacy (if any):

- Data processing.
- Right of access to personal data.
- User's right of information.
- User's objection.
- Right to be forgotten
- Security and privacy of the data.

If there are participants involved in the previously described activities, then they will be informed in detail about the goals and results of the project and the information contribution that will be obtained from them as well as the method that will be used and the reasons for participating. They will be also informed in a clear way that the participation in activities of BeGREEN will not bring any risk or threat to them or their data.

In addition, and according to GDPR, there is an obligation for notification in the case of personal data breach:

- **To the supervisory authority:** In the case of a personal data breach, the controller shall without undue delay and, where feasible, not later than 72 hours after having become aware of it, notify the personal data breach to the supervisory authority competent in accordance with Article 55, unless the personal data breach is unlikely to result in a risk to the rights and freedoms of natural persons. Where the notification to the supervisory authority is not made within 72 hours, it shall be accompanied by reasons for the delay. The processor shall notify the controller without undue delay after becoming aware of a personal data breach.
- **To the data subject:** The controller shall communicate the personal data breach to the data subject without undue delay when the personal data breach is likely to result in a high risk to the rights and freedoms of natural persons.

3 Data Management Plan (DMP)

BeGREEN DMP describes how the data created in BeGREEN will be handled during and after the project. The focus during the project will be on providing privacy for the personalised data that will be used. It is the phase of the project that raises ethical concerns regarding personal data processing. WP5 focuses on the experimentation and demonstration of the use cases. The partners are expected to take into consideration any relevant EU or national legislation regarding processing personal data, i.e., GDPR for the KPI validation if required.

This chapter summarizes the management procedures that will be followed when dealing with the data of relevance for the BeGREEN project. Three main data usage scenarios are envisaged:

- a. Original data produced by the BeGREEN consortium and/or individual members of it, e.g. during the pilot activities, the case studies research and the dissemination activities;
- b. Existing data already in possession of the BeGREEN consortium and/or individual members of it prior to the project's initiation;
- c. Existing data sourced/procured by the BeGREEN consortium and/or individual members of it during the project's timeline.

For each dataset handled in the project, the first level of control/decision making must deal with its *nature*, notably whether it has been (or will be) deemed Confidential, or Anonymised and Public.

Depending on the assessment of nature, the resulting, mandatory action lines can then be summarized as follows:

- For any acknowledged **Confidential** (defined by GDPR [1]) dataset (or data point), the Consortium and/or each Partner in charge of its handling shall control (if existing) or define (if not) the *Licensing rules* and the *Privacy and security measures* (to be) adopted in the process.
- For any acknowledged **Anonymised and Public** dataset (or data point), the only relevant discipline to be clarified is the set of *Open Access rules* that apply to the case.
- Any dataset (or data point) that does not belong to any of the former two categories is subject to an additional level of action by the consortium and/or partner in charge, leading to its classification as either Confidential or Anonymised and Public. In that regard, the two, mutually exclusive action items belonging to this level are:
 - the anonymization for publication action, leading to the migration to the second category of data; or
 - the adoption of appropriate privacy and security measures (very likely the same applied to the category of Confidential data) in case anonymization is not carried out for whatever legitimate reason. In the latter case, i.e., without anonymization, no licensing rules are applicable, i.e., BeGREEN consortium rejects the commercialisation of the personal profiles of human beings as an unethical practice.

The data usage scenarios are used as a basis for discussing the key issues to be examined in relation to each distinct paragraph of the BeGREEN DMP.

In BeGREEN, Personal data, if any, shall be processed in a manner that ensures appropriate security of the data, including protection against unauthorised or unlawful processing and against accidental loss, destruction, or damage, using appropriate technical or organisational measures. All personal data will be handled with appropriate security measures applied. This means:

- Data sets with personal data will be stored in places and under conditions that comply with all GDPR regulations.

- Access to these areas will be managed by each partner and will be given only to people who need to access the data. Access can be retracted if necessary.
- Data sets with personal information could further be shared, only if the datasets are sufficiently secured, e.g., encrypted. In case of theft or loss, these files will be protected by encryption.
- These copies must be deleted as soon as possible and cannot be shared with anyone outside the consortium.

In exceptional cases where the dataset is too large, or it cannot be transferred securely, each partner can share their own datasets through channels that comply with the GDPR.

3.1 Data Summary

The following table summarises the typologies and contents of data collection and production during the project lifetime:

Table 3-1 Summary of relevant data for BeGREEN project

Data Usage Scenarios	Data Types		
	Confidential	Anonymised/Public	Non-anonymised
Original data produced by the consortium	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Survey/interview/sensitive data from research and developments and pilots • Evidence from project pilots • Personal data of end users, stakeholders and policy makers • New contacts established 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Summaries of surveys/interviews • Data in reports of pilot activities • End user data, stakeholders and policy makers data on public display • Contact data within deliverables 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Photos/videos shot during public events and project's workshops • Audio recordings, e.g. telcos • Data in the project internal repositories
Existing data already in possession of the BeGREEN consortium	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data embedded in some of the Background solutions • Contact databases 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data embedded in some of the Background solutions • Data embedded in case studies materials 	N/A
Existing data sourced/procured by the BeGREEN consortium	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Raw data in possession of the pilots or of any third party involved in the pilots 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Free and open data (including from scientific and statistical publications) 	N/A

The main implications of Table 3-1 for the three usage scenarios are the following in *decreasing order of urgency* for the related action lines as well as *increasing order of gravity* for the consequences of any inadvertent behaviour by the members of the consortium:

- For any photos/videos shot during the project internal event and meeting as well as public events related to the project, it is crucial to collect an *informed consent note*¹ from all the participants, with an explicit disclaimer in case of intended publication of those personal images on, e.g., newspapers, internet sites, or social media groups. This will bring the data back into the Confidential category, where it is legitimate to store and/or process it for legitimate reasons.
- For any audio recordings stored, e.g., in the project's official repository (currently BSCW or Microsoft Teams) or in individual partners' repositories, care must be taken of the risk of involuntary disclosure and/or the consequences of misuse for any unauthorized purpose. Same goes for the personal data

¹ Informed means that consent cannot be given before reading and understanding the provisions of extant legislation on personal data protection and the way the partner asking for signature commits to enforcing /abiding by it.

of each partner in the consortium.

- Informed consent forms must be signed (also electronically) by all participants in surveys, interviews and/or pilot activities.
- Informed consent forms are also required when using available contacts (be they pre-existing to the project or created through it) to disseminate information via, e.g., newsletters or dedicated emails. In this respect, the GDPR provisions are particularly binding and must be carefully considered, at least in any doubtful case.
- As a general rule, access conferred to Background knowledge on a loyalty free basis during a project execution does not involve the right to sublicense. Therefore, attention must be paid by each partner of BeGREEN consortium to ensure the respect of licensing conditions at any time and by any member of the team.
- This also applies to any dataset sourced or procured from third parties during the BeGREEN project's lifetime.

3.2 Data Collection

Table 3-2 summarizes the procedures for collecting project related data:

Table 3-2 Summary of BeGREEN data collection procedure

Data Usage Scenarios	Data Types		
	Confidential	Anonymised/Public	Non-anonymised
Original data produced by the consortium	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Surveys • Interviews • Workshops • Meeting with stakeholders • 5G-PPP projects joint sessions • Pilot evaluation sessions 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Newsletters • Publications • Personal Emails • Open access repositories 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Events coverage • A/V conferencing system • Internal repository
Existing data already in possession of the BeGREEN consortium	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Seamless access and use during the project execution 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Seamless access and use during the project execution 	N/A
Existing data sourced/procured by the BeGREEN consortium	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Licensed access and use during the project execution 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Free and open access and use during the project execution 	N/A

An implication of the above table that may not have been evident in the previous one, is that each partner is responsible for the behaviour of their team members, which may also include subcontracted organisations, e.g., specialised press agencies, or even volunteers. The latter circumstance does not exempt the delegate of a certain job in case of improper application of extant norms and rules.

All data will be collected in a digital form - therefore CSV, PDF, Word, xls spreadsheets and text documents will be the prevalent formats. In case of audio and video recordings and images, the most appropriate standards will be chosen and adopted, such as .gif, .jpg, .png, .mp3, .mp4, .mov and .flv. Website pages can be created in .html and/or .xml formats.

It is important to note that email transfer of project related data, such as research output, can become a violation of confidentiality under certain circumstances. Research data in the BeGREEN project is primarily generated by the members of the consortium toward delivering project's stated targets. Most of the data collected for evaluation purposes of the developed technology. BeGREEN research data is expected to be mainly technology related information. Project's pilots are not considering any public member participants, nevertheless, in case, any measurement, trial or demonstration use a participant involvement, special care

will be taken in-line with the anonymisation process described earlier in this document.

3.3 Data Processing

Table 3-3 summarizes the procedures for processing BeGREEN related data that can be envisaged at this project's stage.

Table 3-3 Summary of BeGREEN Data Processing Procedure

Data Usage Scenarios	Data Types		
	Confidential	Anonymised/Public	Non-anonymised
Original data produced by the consortium	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Anonymisation • Visualisation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Qualitative and quantitative evaluation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Selection and destruction • Blurring of identities
Existing data already in possession of the BeGREEN consortium	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Anonymisation • Statistical evaluation • Metadata generation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Visualization • Qualitative and quantitative evaluation • Publication as map services 	N/A
Existing data sourced/procured by the BeGREEN consortium	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Anonymisation • Statistical evaluation • Metadata generation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Visualisation • Qualitative and quantitative evaluation • Publication as map services 	N/A

State of the art productivity tools will be used to process/visualize the data used or generated during the project. Typically, partners are left free to adopt their preferred suite, such as Microsoft Office for PC or Mac, Apple's iWork, and OpenOffice or equivalent. However, the following tools are the ones mainly used by the consortium:

- Adobe Acrobat or equivalent software is used to visualise/create the PDF files;
- Photoshop or equivalent software are used to manipulate images;
- State of the art browsers such as Mozilla Firefox, Google Chrome, Apple Safari and Microsoft Internet Explorer are used to navigate and modify the Internet pages, including the management and maintenance of social media groups;
- MS Teams, Zoom or Skype are the selected tools for audio/video conferencing, which may also serve to manage public webinars;
- Tools like SurveyMonkey and LimeSurvey, SoSciSurvey are used for the administration of online surveys with remotely located participants;
- Dedicated YouTube channels can help broadcast the video clips produced by the consortium to a wider international audience, in addition to the project website;
- Mailchimp or equivalent software is helpful to create, distribute and administer project newsletters and the underlying mailing lists;
- Dedicated mail lists and MS Teams channels are used for the consortium internal communication flows.

3.4 Data Storage

Table 3-4 summarizes the procedures for storing project related data, during and after the project lifetime, and the most frequently used repositories.

Table 3-4 BeGREEN Data Storage Procedure

Data Usage Scenarios	Data Types
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	Confidential	Anonymised/Public	Non-anonymised
Original data produced by the consortium	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Individual partner repository Project repository (BSCW and MS Teams) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Project website Social media (Tweeter, LinkedIn, YouTube) evaluation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Individual partner repositories Project repository
Existing data already in possession of the BeGREEN consortium	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Individual partner repositories Specific software repositories 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Project website Social media (Tweeter, LinkedIn, YouTube) 	N/A
Existing data sourced/procured by the BeGREEN consortium	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Individual partners repositories Cloud repositories Third party repositories 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Project Website Social media (Tweeter, LinkedIn, YouTube) 	N/A

The BSCW tool hosted by the coordinator, IHP, was selected as BeGREEN’s data and information repository. A specific dedicated storage repository was also built, hosted at the same address as the project’s website. However, due to familiarities of some partners and ease of use, it was suggested to use Microsoft Teams as the repository. This is being examined and in case of acceptance by the General Assembly, the migration of all documents and data from the BSCW to the Microsoft Teams will be done, although both BSCW and MS Teams might be used for a while. This includes the project deliverables, dissemination documents, and all technical discussions minutes, slides and reference materials used by the consortium.

Additionally, the project manager will make sure that the official project repository periodically generates back-up files of all data, in case anything may get lost, corrupted, or become unusable at a later stage (including after the project’s end). The same responsibility goes to each partner for the local repositories utilised by them (in some cases, these are handled by large organisations such as Universities; in others, by small organisations or even personal servers or laptops). Collectively, we expect the whole set of outputs to reach the size of up to 1 TB all along the project duration.

Whatever the license that the consortium establishes for final datasets, their intermediate versions will be deemed as *business confidential*, and restricted to circulating only within the consortium.

3.5 Data sharing

Last but not least, Table 3-5 summarizes the procedures for sharing BeGREEN related data in a useful and legitimate manner. When sharing, it is of utmost importance to keep in mind, not only the prescriptions and recommendations of extant rules and norms (including this DMP), as far as confidentiality and personal data protection are concerned, but also the risk of voluntary or involuntary transfer of data from the inside to the outside of the European Economic Area (EEA).

In fact, while the GDPR applies also to the management of EU citizens personal data (for business or research purposes) outside the EU, not all the countries worldwide are subject to bilateral agreements with the EU as far as personal data protection is concerned. For instance, the US based organisations are bound by the so-called EU-U.S. Privacy Shield Framework, which concerns the collection, use, and retention of personal information transferred from the EEA to the US. This makes the transfer of data from the partners to any US based organisation relatively exempt from legal risks. This may not be the same in other countries worldwide, however, and the risk in question is less hypothetical than one may think, if we consider the case of personal sharing of raw data with, e.g., academic colleagues being abroad for the purpose of attending a conference. It is also for this reason that the sharing of non-anonymized data is discouraged for whatever reason, as shown in the table.

Table 3-5 Summary of BeGREEN Data Sharing Procedures

Data Usage Scenarios	Data Types		
	Confidential	Anonymised/Public	Non-anonymised
Original data produced by the consortium	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Personal email communications • Shared repositories 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Project website • Social media (Tweeter, LinkedIn, YouTube) evaluation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Individual partner repositories • Project repository
Existing data already in possession of the BeGREEN consortium	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Personal email communications • Shared access to software repositories 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Project website • Social media (Tweeter, LinkedIn, YouTube) 	N/A
Existing data sourced/procured by the BeGREEN consortium	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Personal email communication • Shared repositories 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Project Website • Social media (Tweeter, LinkedIn, YouTube) 	N/A

BeGREEN project aims to be as open as possible. We take the guidelines developed by Open Knowledge as our starting point.

About the question “how long is it intended that the data remains reusable?” We will adhere to the standard of the chosen repositories for the project. By the end of the project at M30 all data that is not affected by embargo will be made available through the appropriate repositories.

3.6 Data security and access to data

Personal data will need to be stored safely and in a secure environment. Research data is shared between project partners and stored in collaborative online working platforms during the project’s lifetime. Project is Microsoft Teams (BeGREEN Team) hosted and created by Gigasys Solutions for the project. The repositories are meant to support internal communication flows among partners and to exchange anonymized data.

To secure personal data, secure procedures are considered for the repositories, such as login passwords, to identify identities and access managements. The repository is divided into multiple channels based on the WP and other project activities. While the project policy is to maximise partners access to the shared data, the channelization of tasks and storage will provide a higher layer of security as the access to each channel, file and folder is registered in the repository and can be traced back if required.

4 Future Releases of DMP

The DMP is a living document and future releases, if needed, will be adapted to the needs and processes of the experiments and trials, taking into consideration the GDPR guidelines and the project evolution.

This section is a place holder for the contents of next releases of the DMP to bring details of the data that consortium partners are willing to gather.

5 Summary

This deliverable, BeGREEN D1.2, is the document concerning the BeGREEN Data Management Plan (DMP) in fulfilment of the requirements project's DoW. It provides guidelines and directions regarding the data collection, processing, storage, sharing, and related privacy, security, and access issues. It is not expected to use any personal information to be used, gathered, or processed for the project's use cases, demonstrations and tests. Nevertheless, some personal information of the project partners' employees involved in the project, e.g., name, email address, etc., are used for project's communications and they should be kept safe and secure according to guidelines of GDPR [1].

This document's guidelines will be used for data management in all disseminations and communications across the project and to the public. It will be also used for the experimentation and demonstration results analysis, presentation, and documentation.

To ensure the compliance of data handling, of all kinds, in the project to the GDPR guidelines, the Project Management Team will analyse every six months if there is any deviation from the prescription provided in this document with the actual data management procedures applied in the project. This analysis will:

- Secure the current, proposed structure of the DMP against any changes suggested by the gradual start or change of the project activities,
- Integrate the already existing DMP rules with any required add-ons based on the learning process that the project partners will activate throughout the project's lifetime.

The authors hope the presented DMP in this document, BeGREEN D1.2, has fulfilled the goals in providing sufficient and clear guidelines toward a structured and lawful data management across the project activities and along the project lifetime, by:

- Presenting the legislative and regulatory framework, shaping the external context of this DMP in a relatively immutable manner, at least within the timeframe of the project;
- Identifying the fundamental principles of FAIR data handling according to the EC requirements and that the consortium and individual partners are bound to respect;
- Proposing a unitary description of the project's data management lifecycle, a precise requirement of the DoW that has been the conceptual fundamental of the whole document;
- Summarizing the key aspects of data collection, processing, storage and sharing (the typical contents of a DMP) within the proposed data lifecycle elements and particularly highlighting - first and foremost, to the attention of the partners – some key aspects of data management that go beyond the operational link with open access and interfere with privacy and security policies as well as with the way background knowledge and tools will be developed, deployed and customised

BeGREEN DMP will enable all partners to understand the different actions that handling data of different nature, origin and size imply for anyone who need to actively contribute to the successful achievements of the project while staying safe and lawful.

Bibliography

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